

Enabling increased access to space for scientists from all backgrounds

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This paper summarizes the features of the NASA Shuttle Small Payloads Project Office (SSPPO), which was a partner with hundreds of scientists and thousands of students, who flew low-cost science instruments on NASA's Space Shuttle. This paper makes the case that a similar styled implementation project office is needed today to foster the growth and development of the scientific community, enable small low-cost missions, advance and mature instrument technologies readying them for larger science missions, and provide a queue of rideshare payloads. Moreover, such an office would be a focal point for partnerships between Minority-Serving Institutions (MSIs), such as Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCUs), Tribal College and Universities (TCUs), Primarily Undergraduate Institutions (PUIs), and other PhD-granting Universities, advancing these institutions in their capacity to develop space science missions.

1.0 Introduction

In the early years of the NASA Space Shuttle Program, it was recognized that significant launch capacity was not being adequately used. This realization led to the creation, in 1984, of the NASA Shuttle Small Payloads Project Office (SSPPO) whose mission statement was to “To generate the opportunities that maximize science and technology on the Space Shuttle and Space Station for the pioneers of today and tomorrow”. This office worked with the Shuttle flight planning board to manifest, coordinate, and facilitate experiments to fly on the numerous space shuttle flights making use of excess space and lift capacity. Based at the NASA Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC), the SSPPO was the lead organization for integrating and operating external secondary cargo bay payloads on the Space Shuttle. Hundreds of instruments and thousands of experimenters (including students) have been successfully supported through this office. Many of these scientists and students who partnered with the SSPPO built their first space instruments. This white paper will describe the organization and functions of the SSPPO, its successes as well as provide recommendations on how a similar program could be used today to bring new voices and ideas into the NASA Science Mission Directorate to enable breakthrough science.

2.0 Background

Founded back in 1984, the SSPPO’s primary goal was to enable crucial experiments to be conducted in space aboard NASA’s Space Shuttle System. It did this by enabling a diverse customer base, which included NASA, foreign Space Agencies, the DoD, US and foreign universities, commercial entities, and even K-12 grade student groups to fly payloads on the frequent Space Shuttle launches in the Shuttle cargo bay. While in orbit, these payloads would be exposed to space when the cargo bay door opened and could operate for hours and even launch an orbital payload. While PIs were responsible for procuring funding to develop their instrument or technology, they did not have to provide funding to the SSPPO for integrating their instrument onto one of 3 standard carrier systems or the Space Shuttle; the SSPPO was funded by the NASA HQ Human Space Mission Directorate for the work it performed. Each of the 3 SSPPO-developed carrier systems provided standard physical and electrical interfaces as well as various levels of capabilities appropriate to experimenters’ instruments. These standard carriers reduced cost and effort on the part of the PI and included, from the simplest, a flat-plate bolt-down mechanical interfaces, to pressurize-able 2.5 or 5.0 cubic ft canister housings. These carrier systems provided a variety of command and telemetry and operational resources to the PI for their experiments. PIs could apply to any carrier system. Each individual carrier system programs are described in the following paragraphs.

Figure 1: The SSPPO bay carrier system provided the primary physical interface to all SSPPO-provided carrier systems which included the Hitchhiker payload carrier system mounting plates (upper right), the Get Away Special (GAS) carriers (bottom left). A primary avionics unit provided power, telemetry and real-time commanding.

The SSPPO Hitchhiker payload carrier system (Figure 1) was comprised of a suite of mechanical, electronic, and thermal hardware systems that interfaced with the complex cargo bay payload interfaces of the Space Shuttle, and provided simple power, command, and telemetry services to the Hitchhiker PI's instrument. A Hitchhiker operations control center provided commanding and telemetry to the PIs instrument in real-time. Hitchhiker payloads could be mounted to the sides of the cargo bay or span the cargo bay from port to starboard via large cross by truss structures. The suite of Hitchhiker carrier hardware included a small satellite ejection system. Instruments could be mounted at multiple locations on the truss as well as inside 2.5 or 5.0 cubic ft cannisters. Cannisters could be outfitted with a motorized door and a small satellite ejection system. The typical Hitchhiker PI made use of this opportunity to demonstrate new scientific instrumentation, test new technologies and engineering applications, and mature these to a higher TRL. For example, the Capillary Pump Loop (CAPL) Hitchhiker payloads demonstrated new capillary heat pipe technology which was later used on the Earth Observing System (EOS) missions. CAPL flew three times over a 7-year period and twice within a 17-month period. These flights provided the key measurements that were essential for the future of the

EOS missions. The Super Fluid Helium On Orbit Transfer (SHOOT) payload, demonstrated the viability of cryogenic fluid transfer technologies that laid the foundation for future robotic satellite refueling missions. Former NASA Chief Scientist Dr. Jim Garvin flew Laser Altimeter experiments demonstrating that this technique, previously used to map the geography of Mars, is equally applicable for Earth. The Hitchhiker Program successfully flew 26 Hitchhiker payloads with a total of 75 instruments across 27 different Shuttle Missions, from 1984 to 2003.

The SSPPO Get Away Special (GAS) payload carrier system (Figure 2) was a self-contained 2.5 or 5.0 cubic ft. canister, with a 100 or 200 lbs. maximum mass capacity, that housed the PIs instrumentation. GAS payloads were self-contained, could be pressurized to 1 atmosphere with nitrogen or at vacuum pressure, and operated autonomously with no command and telemetry services available; the crew simply turned on, then off, the payloads via switches in the crew cabin. Over time from its origins in the late 1970's the GAS carrier system evolved to include a motorized door assembly, ejection of small satellites, and external power and telemetry services. The GAS program was an ideal venue for high school and university educational communities to gain hands-on engineering experience. For example, the Utah State University (USU) added the GAS program into their curriculum and flew several GAS payloads, including the first GAS payload in 1982; many students from USU went on to successful aerospace careers. Duval High School in Lanham MD, in partnership with the AIAA, created a GAS program engineering class and developed an experiment that looked at the impact of zero gravity on cockroaches. The GAS program successful flew 167 payloads on 39 Shuttle Missions from 1982 to 1998. Every year, about 9 payloads were flown with 34% classified as educational payloads, 41% commercial/international, and 24% government payloads.

Figure 2: (left) Exploded view of GAS Cannister Carrier System w Experiment, (right) Representative GAS experimenters in various stages of integration

The Student Experiment Module (SEM) payload carrier system (Figure 3) was a sub carrier system contained within a 5.0 cubic ft. Canister and was restricted to K-12 educational communities. The SEM systems evolved from the difficulty younger educational communities

were having developing a full GAS payload, which required not just development of an experiment, but all the supporting subsystems, i.e., structural, thermal, power and data. To enable these young students to focus on developing just their experiment, the SSPPO developed the SEM subcarrier. Similar to GAS, this carrier provided only simple power and data interfaces. Experiment data was recorded and viewed post flight. SEM was specifically designed to foster student involvement in STEM careers through NASA Space Shuttle missions. The SSPPO outreach activities, via the SEM program, was a major contributor to NASA's STEM outreach activities at the time. For example, in the aftermath of September 11, 2001, terrorist attacks on New York City, the SSPPO SEM team partnered with the Rose Center for Earth and Space in NYC and extended an invitation to local elementary school children to fly a SEM experiment (Figure 3). The students SEM experiments flew aboard STS 107 Columbia. With the loss of the STS 107 mission, the SSPPO arranged to fly their experiments on a Russian Proton resupply mission, whose crew transferred the SEM experiments to the ISS and were returned via STS 114 In July of 2005. The SEM program successfully flew 140 individual SEM experiments across 14 SEM payloads, on 11 different Shuttle Missions, and involved over 10,000 K-12 students, between 1996 and 2003.

Figure 3: The Student Experiment Module (SEM) payload carrier system

In total, the SSPPO had either a GAS, SEM, or Hitchhiker experiment on 57 of the 115 Shuttle missions between STS-4 in 1982 and STS 107 in 2003, flying 382 experiments before the office was disbanded after the Columbia disaster. Some examples successful flights made possible by this office are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: (Left) STP-1 payload aboard STS-39; April of 1991 (Bottom Left), SAC-A and (Right) DoD Mighty Sat after deployment aboard STS 88, December 1998.

3.0 Summary

These successes were made possible by the SSPPO hands-on support of PIs. The program provided experiment to carrier integration, supported carrier to Shuttle integration, flight and ground safety, and implemented payload flight operations and most importantly by providing key hardware systems such that PIs could focus on their experiments. The SSPPO provided integrated payload mission management interfaces to JSC & KSC; generated all required program documentation as well as provided training to PIs to understand NASA requirements. The SSPPO managed and worked to minimize requirements on PIs for documentation, meetings, safety reviews, etc. as much as possible. Because the SSPPO staff were long-term frequent flyers aboard NASA's space shuttle, they were able to maintain lessons learned, into payload integration processes (safety certification, mission integration, etc.) that led to faster and more efficient integration of SSPPO-managed Shuttle payloads reducing mission costs.

Finally, locating the SSPPO within NASA's GSFC's Special Payloads Division (SPD) was another key to its success. The SPD was GSFC "skunk works" organization which specialized in fast turn -

around Class D, and “sub-Cass D” missions. Locating the SSPPO at GSFC also took advantage of that Center’s scientific and engineering expertise, as well as its experience in working with launch service providers; The SSPPO GSFC staff was adept at speaking and understanding both the language and concerns of the scientific and educational communities and the language and concerns of the JSC and KSC Shuttle Program payload integration, safety, and launch services communities. Thus, the SSPPO provided significant support to science PIs through simple carrier hardware systems interfaces *and* a cultural translation interface for the PI to the world of crewed space flight, thus freeing the PI to focus their resources on developing their experiments, and not dealing with the complexities and bureaucracy of a NASA mission such as those hosted on the Space Shuttle.

4.0 A Case for Action

There are a number of concerns expressed by today’s scientific community that have surfaced through National Academy of Science reports. The NAS report on Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Accessibility (DEIA) states “NASA needs long-term, sustained investments in effective activities that inspire, educate, train, and mentor female scientists and scientists of color to engage in NASA mission-related work and leadership”; and says “SMD provide consistent and adequate funding for post-secondary education through professional career level STEM initiatives explicitly centered on DEIA”. NAS notes that “HBCUs, MSIs, and non-Ph.D.-granting institutions receive less federal funding than many other universities, reflecting long-standing disparities in research capacity and infrastructure”, and that “NASA use its resources to expand support for diverse external potential PIs”. The process PIs need to navigate in order to have their proposals selected require significant resources sometimes beyond the capacity of their supporting institution. Unless NASA takes action to address these concerns, there will continue to be barriers to entry of new PI’s, especially those under-represented institutions such as HBCU, MSI, etc.

The NAS in the Heliophysics Mid Decadal Review states that “in order to achieve a 3-year launch frequency between Explorers missions”. The report recommends that “NASA develop a more efficient management environment and an improved contract/grant structure, both to reduce mission cost and to shorten the interval from Announcement of Opportunity (AO) to launch; and further recommended that NASA (1) adopt new procedures to facilitate a more cost-efficient implementation of smaller satellites and instruments using game-changing small-sat technology, and (2) continue to strive toward reduced launch costs, for example through ride sharing.”

Clearly, something more is being called for than what is presently offered by NASA, to address these concerns.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

The SSPPO program described above was wildly successful enabling scientists from all backgrounds, and students, to gain access to space and make new discoveries. This was possible through a tiered approach of support and standardized NASA-provided hardware systems. Experienced PIs could design and fly entire science missions. Those with less space-flight experience could depend on subsystems and commanding support or even fly in a lab-like environment (1 atmosphere). High school and K-12 students were even supported. **We recommend that a new support program be implemented to enable new PIs to perform space-based experiments on stand-alone space-flight missions or on**

crewed or uncrewed Artemis missions. A Small Payloads Project Office, modeled in part like the SSPPO, would provide a single interface between potential PIs and flight opportunities. Such an organization must provide significant systems and integration engineering and project management support. This organization would foster partnerships between Minority-Serving Institutions (MSIs), such as Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCUs), Tribal College and Universities (TCUs), Primarily Undergraduate Institutions (PUIs), and other PhD-granting Universities and mature these institutions to compete for larger missions (e.g. Explorers). By enabling new voices and new ideas, breakthrough science results will follow.